

A fatty alcohol with antioxidant potential isolated from *Leea asiatica* leaves

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Abstract : A fatty alcohol was isolated from the leaves of *Leea asiatica* (Leeaceae). This is the first time when any compound was isolated from the plant. Antioxidant study of the isolated compound (fraction) revealed that fraction possess strong antioxidant activity. The compound at 20 µg/ml concentration possesses 39.12% DPPH• scavenging effect and 35.26% NO• scavenging effect respectively. Thus the isolated fatty alcohol could be a future drug molecule in the treatment of various oxidative stress related diseases.

Keywords : *Leea asiatica*, fatty alcohol, leaf, antioxidant.

Introduction

The progress of modern medicine primarily rooted in plant based traditional medicines and therapies. Active constituent from plants have historically been precious as a source of therapeutic agents¹. A number of drugs have been incorporated in the pharmacopoeias through the study of ethnopharmacology. According to an assessment nearly 75% of the herbal drugs used worldwide were integrated from traditional/folk medicine².

Leea asiatica (L.) Ridsdale (Family : Leeaceae), a folk medicinal plant of India used by ethnic people in the treatment of worm infection, wound, eye diseases, bone fracture, diabetes and gastrointestinal disorders^{3,4}. Our previous investigation reported the fractions of *L. asiatica* leave possess anthelmintic and antioxidant activity⁵. This study was undertaken to isolate few antioxidant compounds from the leaves of *Leea asiatica*.

Results and discussion

Free radical scavenging activity :

Sub-fractionation of *L. asiatica* ethyl acetate fraction (EFLA) yielded 7 fractions. 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picryl-hydrazyl

radical (DPPH•) scavenging assay of all sub-fractions revealed that LA-4 produced highest activity followed by LA-2, LA-7, LA-3. While, LA-2 showed highest nitric oxide radical (NO•) scavenging activity followed by LA-4, LA-7 and LA-1 (Table 1).

In our previous investigation we have found that EFLA possess significant DPPH• scavenging (IC₅₀ = 9.5 µg/ml) and NO• scavenging activity (IC₅₀ = 13.0 µg/ml). EFLA at 32 µg/ml concentration possess 76.22% DPPH•, and 80 µg/ml concentration it possess 78.3% NO• scavenging effect⁵. In this study, at 20 µg/ml concentration LA-4, LA-2, LA-7 possess 49.90, 43.12, 39.12% DPPH• scavenging effect and 44.92, 48.03, 35.26% NO• scavenging effect respectively.

DPPH scavenging activity is based on the principle that antioxidants compound reduces the stable DPPH radical to a yellow colored diphenyl-picrylhydrazine^{6,7}. The sub-fractions especially LA-4, LA-2, LA-7 have exhibited strong activity, which may be accredited to a direct role in trapping free radicals by donating hydrogen atom. NO is a biologically active radical and an imperative pleiotropic mediator of several physiological processes^{8,9}.

Table 1. Antioxidant activity of sub-fractions of *L. asiatica*

Fractions	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Percentage inhibition	
		DPPH \bullet scavenging assay	NO \bullet scavenging assay
LA-1	10	10.10 \pm 0.10	20.34 \pm 0.24
	20	19.04 \pm 0.11	29.06 \pm 0.31
LA-2	10	36.09 \pm 0.18	35.05 \pm 0.29
	20	43.12 \pm 0.22	48.03 \pm 0.38
LA-3	10	22.03 \pm 0.08	8.98 \pm 0.08
	20	27.40 \pm 0.09	13.46 \pm 0.15
LA-4	10	40.00 \pm 0.44	31.47 \pm 0.029
	20	49.90 \pm 0.31	44.92 \pm 0.27
LA-5	10	7.30 \pm 0.13	5.38 \pm 0.09
	20	8.13 \pm 0.18	18.33 \pm 0.12
LA-6	10	5.40 \pm 0.04	3.14 \pm 0.07
	20	14.80 \pm 0.35	9.89 \pm 0.05
LA-7	10	32.92 \pm 0.31	28.99 \pm 0.17
	20	39.12 \pm 0.40	35.26 \pm 0.22

Values are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. ($n = 3$).

NO \bullet is relatively stable but can react with superoxide which results generation of potent and toxic oxidant peroxynitrite. Thus sub-fractions (especially LA-4, LA-2, LA-7) significantly scavenge NO \bullet which further expands their as a potent antioxidant.

Structure elucidation :

TLC was performed for *L. asiatica* fractions (LA-1 to LA-7), but only LA-7 showed single spot, which indicated that only LA-7 isolated as pure form, other fractions may contain a mixture of antioxidant constituents. Thus LA-7 was selected for spectral analysis. Chemical and spectral analysis (IR, PMR, ^{13}C NMR, Mass) revealed the LA-7 is a fatty alcohol and the tentative structure of LA-7 is, $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{50}\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$.

IR spectral analysis showed a broad absorption band between 3000–3500 cm^{-1} suggesting presence of hydroxyl group and a sharp band at 2975.65 cm^{-1} for CH_3 group. A peak was observed at 2928.62 cm^{-1} for $-\text{CH}_2-$ and 1046 cm^{-1} for C-O. ^1H NMR spectroscopy analysis showed a triplet at δ 0.82 ppm for terminal methyl group of the compound. Triplets or multiplets at δ 1.28 and 1.02 ppm suggested fifty methylene groups. The pair of doublets at δ 3.85 and 4.4 are due to a methylene group under oxygen function ($-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$). ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy data showed δ value at 59.79 ppm for CH_2OH . ^{13}C

NMR signals in between δ 48.73–49.58 ppm and 48.51 ppm were identified as fifty $-\text{CH}_2-$ carbons (with negligible intensity) and a signal at δ 26.76 ppm indicates terminal CH_3 group. Mass spectroscopic study showed molecular ion peak at m/z 746 (M^+) and the base peak at m/z 663 for the fragment $[(\text{CH}_2)_{45}\text{CH}_2\text{OH}]^+(\text{M}^+ + 2)$.

Antioxidant components are important for their diverse pharmacological action and choice of interest because of their protective physiological role against oxidative stress induced diseases such as cardiovascular, neurodegenerative, gastrointestinal, endocrine diseases, and cancer¹⁰. Results suggested that isolated compound possess potent antioxidant activity and may be a future drug candidate against oxidative stress related diseases, though further investigation is required in this regards. Antioxidant activity of other fractions also indicated that several other antioxidant compounds present in the fractions and isolation of those could be helpful in future.

Experimental

Plant material, extraction and fractionation :

Leaves of *Leea asiatica* (L.) Ridsdale were collected from Tripura, India and duly authenticated by Dr. B. K. Datta, Department of Botany, Tripura University, Tripura, India (Voucher specimen : TU/BOT/HEB/SS23072011c). Dried leaves of *L. asiatica* were pulverized and extracted with methanol using Soxhlet apparatus. The methanol extract was further fractionated using the following solvents in the order of increasing polarity viz. petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and methanol. The yields afforded petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, and methanol fraction were 6.8%, 40.3% and 37.5% w/w respectively.

Sub-fractionation of more active fraction :

In our previous study, we found that among the three fractions ethyl acetate fraction (EFLA) possess better *in vitro* and *ex vivo* antioxidant activity⁵. Thus EFLA was selected for further sub-fractionation. EFLA was subjected for column chromatography to isolate pure compound by using column chromatography. Silica gel (60–120 sieve) was used as stationary phase, benzene was used as mobile phase. There were 7 bands distinctly visualized for EFLA which were collected serially. Isolated 7 components of *L. asiatica* and recorded as LA-1 to LA-7.

Antioxidant activity and selection of sub-fraction :

DPPH• and NO• scavenging activity of all sub-fractions (LA-1 to LA-7) were evaluated by taking 2 fixed concentrations (10 and 20 µg/ml).

Free radical scavenging capacity was measured in terms of hydrogen-donating or radical scavenging ability, using stable DPPH radical. Briefly, 1.0 ml of 0.1 mM DPPH methanolic solution was added to 3.0 ml of sample solution. The mixture was kept in room temperature in the dark for 30 min and absorbance was recorded at 517 nm¹¹.

To estimate NO• scavenging activity, 4.0 ml of sample solution were mixed with 1.0 ml of 25 mM sodium nitroprusside solution. The reaction mixture (2.0 ml) after 2 h incubation at 37 °C was mixed with 1.2 ml Griess reagent. The absorbance was measured immediately at 570 nm¹².

Isolation and characterization isolated sub-fraction :

Based on antioxidant activity 3 sub-fractions of *L. asiatica* were selected for further analysis. Selected sub-fractions (LA-2, LA-4, LA-7) were subjected for TLC. Only LA-7 showed single spot. Therefore LA-7 considered pure isolated compound and selected for spectral analysis. LA-7 was subjected to IR spectroscopy in KBr (Perkin-Elmer Spectrum Version 10.03.06), ¹H and C13 NMR (Bruker DRX-300) and mass spectroscopy (ESI-HRMS, Agilent 6520 Q-ToF).

Conclusions

In present study, a chemical constituent was isolated first time from *L. asiatica*. The isolated compounds a fatty alcohol from *L. asiatica* showed potent antioxidant

activities which could be a future drug molecule in the treatment of various oxidative stress related diseases. Further study should be carried out to isolate the other individual components present in the plant and their specific pharmacological activity.

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